

A MODEL FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ANALYTICAL THINKING IN FUTURE PEDAGOGUES

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Abstract: Analytical thinking, the model of its development is analyzed in the article, and organizational steps and pedagogical aspects are based on it.

Key words: analytical thinking, methodological support, regulatory and legal support, practical-applied (empirical) function, axiological, criterion.

INTRODUCTION. In the conditions of today's globalization, education of personnel with deep thinking and strong scientific potential is an important guarantee for the sustainable development of every society. In our country, there is a growing need for potential higher education institutions and competitive personnel with a new worldview that will develop in them. That is why it is important pedagogical requirements to evaluate the effectiveness of the pedagogical process aimed at developing analytical thinking in future pedagogues and to introduce new approaches by identifying shortcomings in the current situation.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. As part of the research, the development of a model for the development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues was defined as the goal. This type of model helps to find tools for managing the process of developing analytical thinking in future pedagogues, as well as, according to V.A. Slastenin, to reflect the functions of controlling the researched processes, which, according to V.A. Slastenin, allow to achieve the difference between the initial and final state of the level of preparation of students as subjects of the model .

In our research, the process of developing analytical thinking in future pedagogues was the object of modeling, and the content and methodical system of developing analytical thinking in them was the subject.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The following functions were considered in the modeling of the required pedagogical system:

- methodological support function. The implementation of this function is related to regulatory and legal documents and the social order that defines the theoretical basis for the development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues;
- regulatory and legal support function. This function requires determining the principles, content, tasks, pedagogical conditions, diagnostic tools for the development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues;
- methodological support function. It requires clarifying the methodological (content, form, methods and tools) conditions for the development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues;
- practical-applied (empirical) function. This function allows solving a number of tasks: formation of knowledge and stable motives for the development of analytical thinking in

future pedagogues, analysis of the researched process and making certain corrections; evaluation and analysis of results, etc.

The following rules were used as the theoretical-methodological basis of modeling the researched process:

- systematic, personal activity-oriented, reflexive approaches;
- theory of pedagogical design, modeling of developmental educational environment;
- theoretical foundations of creating didactic and methodical support;
- the formation of axiological direction and the concept of civic education;
- theoretical and methodological foundations of analytical thinking development.

The model for the development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues reflected goal-oriented, theoretical-methodological, content-related, organizational and result-oriented components [6].

The goal-oriented block plays a leading role for other blocks of the system of developing analytical thinking in future pedagogues. Based on the clarification of the content of this block, the educational standard and social order, regulatory and legal bases in the field of research were determined. The goals and objectives of the model were also clarified.

The development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues was defined as a social order through the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law "On Education" in the new version, and the State Education Standard of higher education.

The analysis of educational standards and legal documents on the development of analytical thinking showed the need to optimize educational and preventive work aimed at developing analytical thinking in future pedagogues.

The goal orientation of the system is determined by the achievement of certain results. Clarification of the goal is carried out by focusing on a number of questions that the developed system should answer. In order to successfully solve the problem of developing analytical thinking in future pedagogues, the final result of this process should be clearly reflected [4].

The purpose of the model was defined as the development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues.

During the development of the model, it was envisaged to solve the following tasks:

- clarification of methodological approaches to the development of a model for the development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues;
- clarification of the block structure of the model;
- reveal the relationship between model blocks and elements;
- to describe the block structure and elements of the model.

The above-mentioned goals and tasks of developing analytical thinking in future pedagogues are related to complex methodological approaches.

To teachers-pedagogues in order to organize a new teaching methodology and fulfill educational standards in the development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues:

- to deeply understand the purpose and content of the lesson;
- organization of the lesson process based on correct and accurate sources;
- having pedagogical activity in terms of mastering and teaching the subject;
- in-depth knowledge and ability to use the methodology and possibilities of interdisciplinary integration;

ensuring the proportionality of the concepts of era and time with specific sources, events and events;

to have the ability to connect additional information and resources related to the topic.

To pay particular attention to the development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues, to teach them to think more freely and independently in this process, to move from subject-object relations to subject-subject relations, i.e. person-oriented organizing the educational process, as well as creating conditions for their independent education, analyzing their scientificity, novelty and reliability based on the study of the information they have obtained independently, providing them with the latest and most reliable information, students' the need to pay special attention to the exchange of information was determined in the coordination of activities [2].

The level of development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues was determined based on the following criteria (low, medium, high).

Based on these criteria, it helps to determine the state of development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues.

It is necessary to effectively use the possibilities of interactive educational methods in the development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues.

Today, project-based education shows high efficiency in the development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues. Pedagogical goals given in the method of projects are a method of working out the details of scientific or practical problems. At the end of this process, a concrete and realistic result is determined. The main task of this method is to create conditions for students to independently acquire analytical qualities in the process of solving practical tasks or problems. These conditions create opportunities for the development of analytical thinking. In addition, this method incorporates various other methods: research, problematic, creative methods. In this process, the teacher performs the duties of a developer, manager, expert, and consultant.

If this method is put on the first level in the educational process, it is possible to talk about the use of project education technology. It serves to develop project activity in future pedagogues. Therefore, in this, future pedagogues will analyze the problems in the field of science, clarify their foundations, apply design technology to search for a solution, conduct research, analyze and systematize the obtained information, develop reflexive skills to evaluate the quality and effectiveness of the solution found. forms.

In the development of analytical thinking of future pedagogues, socio-humanities have the following tasks: to give a social direction to their acquired knowledge; follow the principle of gradualism in acquiring knowledge; increase their independence and activity; creating an inner desire to acquire knowledge and think about it; applying acquired knowledge to students' practical activities; such as critical thinking, analytical analysis, logical conclusion of future personnel [5, 7].

All such tasks are carried out in the process of thinking and discussing, communicating. It is very effective for future pedagogues to exchange ideas in the process of more discussions, debates, and open discussions about scientific problems. In this process, they acquire the skills of solving scientific problems, understanding them, analyzing scientific phenomena, and critically approaching the obtained results. In this way, activity with new content is formed in them. Scientific phenomena and information become firmly established in their minds, and they learn to justify their point of view logically with full confidence, their analytical thinking is stabilized, because independently acquired knowledge is socially oriented. The following

tasks are set before this process: to form the ability of future pedagogues to fully justify their point of view scientifically; such as convincing them that all the conclusions they stated are logically based and do not have contradictions [4].

Analytical way of thinking requires future pedagogues to compare newly acquired scientific knowledge with existing knowledge, analyze, synthesize and harmonize. This forms their critical thinking, independent approach to information and increases curiosity. As a result, their level of readiness to make independent decisions increases. They include the qualities of independence, responsibility, openness to communication, activity, striving for a goal, hard work, and not being afraid of difficulties.

CONCLUSION. In our opinion, the use of innovative educational technologies in the development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues creates an opportunity to develop their professional competence. Such opportunities develop on the basis of contextual and project-based educational technologies. In this process, the needs, motivations, and goals of future pedagogues in education change radically. In the development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues, the main attention is focused on the formation of their scientific-pedagogical consciousness and the development of the ability to think in a new way.

The classification marks of the technology of development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues, developed by us, are of great importance in enriching students' worldview, thinking and thinking with ideas of humanization in the process of training in order to develop educational work.

Based on the above points, it can be said that the content and essence of the development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues is a process aimed at turning a new imagination, idea, vision into a project, and a project into a technology.

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